

FRACTURE MECHANISM OF MECHANICALLY FASTENED CFRTP

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1 Introduction

In recent years, energy reduction is important. In this regards, the establishment of lightweight technology and high-efficiency recycling technology for vehicles have been researched to cope with the global environmental problem. To improve fuel efficiency, CFRP (carbon fiber reinforced plastics) have been widely used as high performance structural material for aerospace and leisure applications because of its high specific strength and high specific stiffness. However, the wide range of success in the market has not yet been achieved due to the high cost and the low productivity[1]. Recently, CFRTP (carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics) is expected as lightweight material for automobiles because of its promising high-mechanical properties, high-cycle and low-cost manufacturing, and high-recyclability. In the current manufacturing process of automobile, joining has been one of the key technologies because it is easier to fabricate the vehicle body for improving productivity. Joining can be classified into three types: bonding, welding and mechanical fastening. Although many assembly problems can be solved by bonding or welding joints, there are still many cases where only mechanical fastening is capable of meeting certain design requirements[1].

We especially focused on mechanical fastening using CF/PP, which is carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene. Polypropylene (PP) is developed by Japanese METI-NEDO project "Development of Sustainable Hyper Composite Materials Technology". PP shows lower cost and higher cycle performance than the other thermoplastics. However, it has the characteristics of relatively low adhesiveness and elasticity. It is chemically modified to improve adhesiveness between CF and PP.

In this paper, in order to investigate fracture process of mechanical fastening, we conducted tensile tests on mechanically fastened joints of CFRTP. The tests were conducted with reference to JIS K7080-2[2] which standardized the testing methods for bearing strength of CFRP.

Unlike CFRTS (carbon fiber reinforced thermosetting resin), the fracture process of CFRTP has yet to be revealed. Actually, the JIS standard is for FRTS and there are no standard for tensile strength test of CFRTP. In this research, we focused on the fracture process of CFRTP, especially the initial fracture which is important in mechanical designs.

2 Experimental procedure

2.1 Materials

Three types of CFRTP were used in this research; QISO-TP, CTT and CMT as shown in Fig. 1 QISO-TP and CTT use continuous CF/PP prepreg tapes. QISO-TP was formed by laminated molding of uni-directional (UD) prepreg tapes with carbon fiber volume fraction (V_f) of 50%. The laminates were fabricated through a process of stacking prepreg cut tapes to form a quasi-isotropic plate[3], heating them up by hot plate, adding pressure on the molds concurrently and cooling down them in the end. Chopped carbon fiber Tape reinforced Thermoplastics (CTT) plate was made from the same prepreg tapes (35mm length) as QISO-TP by the expert Toyobo, because of the advanced technique needed in the molding process. Carbon fiber Mat reinforced Thermoplastics (CMT) use discontinuous CF reinforced isotropic plates of which carbon fiber volume fraction is 20%. CMT plates are made by expert Toray. CMT was also reheated and pressurized to obtain a plate of certain thickness. To equalize the condition, the pressures added on the molds are all 5.0MPa.

In order to make a comparison with CFRTP, we also tested CFRTS, which was composed of epoxy resin. QISO-TS plate was obtained by laminating UD prepreg sheets in the same sequence as QISO-TP, and pressuring and heating them concurrently. The sheet is made by the expert Mitsubishi rayon. Carbon fiber volume fraction of CFRTS is 50%.

Table 1 shows the materials used in this research. As referred to above, the base materials of QISO-TP and CTT, carbon fiber prepreg tape, are the same.

Fig. 2 shows the molding conditions of these materials. The upper graph is the molding process of CFRTP and the lower one is that of CFRTS. Though CFRTP needs higher molding pressure and temperature than CFRTS, CFRTS requires longer molding time than CFRTP.

2.2 Test Method

In this research, all specimens were the same size; the width was 36(mm), the edge distance was 18(mm), and the diameter of the hole was 6(mm). Fig. 3 shows the specimen size.

We conducted tensile strength tests based on JIS K7080-2 "Carbon fiber reinforced plastics-Testing methods for bearing strength-Part2: Orthotropic and Quasi-isotropic long fiber laminates". The crosshead speed is 1.0 mm/min. We measured the load and the displacement of the hole. Specimens were attached to the jig as shown in Fig.3. The clamping torque was 3.0 (Nm). The displacement was measured by a clip-gage, which was attached to the jig. In addition, we used an acoustic emission (AE) sensor to monitor the damage occurrences in CFRP[4]. Fig. 4 shows a schema of the experiment. The measurements were conducted 5 times for each material.

After the tensile tests, we not only observed specimens but also made more precise observation of the state of carbon fiber with a computed tomography scan (CT scan).

In accordance with the JIS standard, bearing stress vs. bearing strain curves were derived. The bearing stress σ (MPa) and the stress at the ultimate failure stress σ_m are expressed as

$$\sigma = P/dt \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_m = P_m/dt \quad (2)$$

where P (N) is the load, P_m (N) is the failure load, d (mm) is the diameter of the hole, t (mm) is the thickness of the specimen.

The bearing strain ε is given by

$$\varepsilon = \delta/d \quad (3)$$

where δ (mm) is the displacement of the clip-gage. From these curves, bearing elasticity and offset bearing failure stress are obtained.

Fig. 5 shows Load-Displacement curve of QISO-TS. From this curve, we could get Stress-Strain curves as shown in Fig. 6.

The bearing elasticity modulus E is defined as

$$E = (\sigma_H - \sigma_L) / (\varepsilon_H - \varepsilon_L) \quad (4)$$

where σ_H and σ_L are the stresses of 40% and 15% of σ_m , respectively. ε_H and ε_L are the strains at each point of σ_H and σ_L .

In this test, the initial failure is regarded as the offset bearing failure stress σ_{im} . The stress was obtained by evaluating the stress at the intersecting point of the stress-strain curve and the line, which is expressed as follow

$$E(\varepsilon - \varepsilon_H - 2) - (\sigma - \sigma_H) = 0 \quad (5)$$

Fig. 7 shows these parameters for typical CTT mechanical fastening joint.

In fracture process, different types of failure modes can be seen. Two major failure modes are bearing and net tension failure. Which failure modes specimens show depends on the compressive strength. The Bearing stress σ_b is expressed as follow

$$\sigma_b = P/dt \quad (6)$$

And the net tension stress σ_n is given by

$$\sigma_n = P/(w-d)t \quad (7)$$

where w (mm) is the width. If the net tension stress of the specimen is lower than the bearing stress, the failure mode is net tension. Fig. 8 shows the two types of failure modes.

3. Experimental result

3.1 Failure modes

First of all, we mention about the failure mode and the fracture stress.

Fig. 9-Fig. 12 show each failure mode of QISO-TS, QISO-TP, CTT, CMT. The QISO-TS, QISO-TP and CTT specimens showed bearing failure mode. On the other hand, the CMT specimens showed net tension failure. Because the failure mode was much affected by the clamping torque[6], we conducted the other CTT test in the case where the clamping force was 0.1[Nm]. The failure mode shows in the right side of Fig. 12. The specimens of low clamping torque showed bearing failure mode as other CFRTP specimens.

Fig. 13- Fig. 15 show each stress-strain curves of the CFRTP. These curves got from the load-displacement curves as CFRTS. From these stress-strain curves, we could evaluate each offset bearing stress and ultimate failure stress. The failure stress of QISO-TS was larger than that of QISO-TP. From the shape of stress-strain curve of QISO-TS, it was also clear that once QISO-TS reached the maximum load, the fracture process proceeded quickly. The $\sigma_{offset} / \sigma_{ultimate}$ of QISO-TS which equaled to the offset bearing stress divided by the ultimate bearing stress was 0.86. On the other hand, that of QISO-TP was 0.78 and that of CTT was 0.76. It means that CFRTP materials showed more ductile fracture process than CFRTS.

Next, we mention about the difference between QISO-TP and CTT. Fig. 18 shows the comparison of offset failure stress and ultimate failure stress in QISO-TP and CTT tests. Both the offset and ultimate failure stresses of CTT were equal to those of QISO-TP. This is because both materials used the same carbon fiber prepreg tapes. However, each shape of stress-strain graph was different as shown in Fig. 13 and Fig. 14. The stress drop which was happened when the crack advance occurs in specimens of QISO-TP was bigger than that of CTT. To make clear this difference, we focused on the acoustic emissions, which is discussed below.

Regarding CMT, at high clamping torque, the failure mode was net tension failure though the other type of CFRTP showed bearing failure mode (the left of Fig. 12). This meant that the bearing strength of CMT was higher than the other materials. Because the clamping torque affected the bearing stress, to calculate the bearing stress, we conducted one more test at the torque of 0.1[Nm] which was approximately as tight as the clamping torque tighten by hand.

By lessening the clamping torque, the specimens showed bearing failure mode (the right of Fig. 12). Fig. 17 shows the comparison of the bearing stress. The effect on the clamping torque is shown in Fig. 17. There were not many gaps in the ultimate failure stresses, but when the torque is 0.1 (Nm) the offset failure stress. It is clear that high clamping torque strengthens up the bearing stress of the specimen especially in CMT specimens.

As shown in Table 2, compared to the bearing stress of QISO-TP or CTT, the bearing stress of CMT was much lower than that of the other materials. But we should consider that the carbon fiber volume fraction

is 20 (%). It was relatively enough strength for the low V_f materials compared the other materials of which V_f was 50(%).

3.2 Acoustic emission

To compare the difference among the CFRTP materials, we focused on acoustic emission. Fig. 18- Fig. 21 show each load response and AE amplitude vs. displacement in QISO-TS specimens. As shown in Fig. 18, before the first declination of the curve at about 15,000 (N), the number of event increased at about 10,000 (N). This means that some failure occurred before the failure with the load decrease. After the beginning of the fracture, we observed many high amplitude signals. The same is equally true of CFRTP materials.

Regarding QISO-TP (Fig. 19), until displacement reached 1.2 (mm), there were no detectable AE events. But when the displacement increased further, AE events began. At this point, the specimen display some cracks. This crack was so small that we couldn't inspect it by naked eye[4]. Subsequently a drastic rise of the number of the events was observed and after that, the stress-strain curve declined with some clear cracks which were seen around the hole. Fig. 22 is the picture which was gotten by CT scan. Once initial failure occurred, the high amplitude AE events (70-100dB) continuously happened with the declination of the load.

As to CTT (Fig. 20), after the initial failure happened, most AE amplitudes of CTT were lower than 80dB though those of QISO-TP were lower than 70dB. CTT specimens showed fracture with larger AE amplitude than QISO-TP specimens. We can say that these frequent events with high amplitude make the stress-strain curves of CTT smoother.

Fig. 21 shows the plot of AE amplitude of CMT. CMT fracture process was accompanied with frequent AE events which had the amplitude as high as CTT.

As CTT specimens, the bearing stress-bearing strain curve is smooth. We can presume that it was caused by the character of the discontinuous of CMT or CTT.

4. Conclusions

It became clear that bearing failure stress was much smaller than the ultimate failure stress.

The percentage of the offset failure stress to ultimate failure stress of CFRTP is lower than that of CFRTS. It is because CFRTP is more ductile than CFRTS. Therefore, CFRTP shows a gradual process of bearing failure.

Although the failure stress in QISO-TP and CTT specimens were approximately equal for their materials, the scale of fracture differs in degree. In QISO-TP or CTT specimens, the ultimate failure stress is 1.3 times as large as the offset failure stress, We can say that we should consider not only the ultimate failure stress but also the initial failure stress in mechanical design.

In CMT specimens, the failure stress and the failure mode is highly subject to the influence of the clamping force. Especially the bearing strength is strengthened by enlarging the bolt axial tension.

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Fig. 1. Fiber reinforced form[6]

Table 1 Materials Used

	Specimen Name	Base Material	$V_f(\%)$
CFRTS	QISO-TS	TS prepreg sheet	50
CFRTP	QISO-TP	Carbon fiber prepreg tape	50
	CTT	Carbon fiber Tape reinforced Thermoplastics prepreg sheet	50
	CMT	Carbon fiber Mat reinforced Thermoplastics prepreg sheet	20

Fig. 2 Molding condition (Upper: CFRTP, Lower: CFRTS)

Fig. 3. Specimen size

Fig. 4. Tensile strength test.

Fig. 7. Typical Bearing stress-Bearing strain curve in bearing tests of CTT specimens[5]

Fig. 8. Two major types of failure modes[1]

Fig. 5. Load-Displacement curve (QISO-TS)

Fig. 6. Stress-Strain curve (QISO-TS)

Fig. 9. Failure mode (QISO-TS)

Fig. 10. Failure mode (QISO-TP)

Fig. 13. Stress-Strain curve of QISO-TP

Fig. 11. Failure mode (CTT)

Fig. 14. Stress-Strain curve of CTT

Fig. 12. Failure mode of CMT (left: the torque of 3.0(Nm), right: 0.1(Nm))

Fig. 15. Stress-Strain curve of CMT (clamping torque is 3.0(Nm))

Table 2 Offset and ultimate failure stress of each material

	QISO-TS	QISO-TP	CTT	CMT
$V_f(\%)$	50	50	50	20
Offset failure stress σ_{int} (MPa)	885.1	604.11	630.50	377.82
Ultimate failure stress σ_{ult} (MPa)	1025.0	820.63	827.20	399.43
$\sigma_{int} / \sigma_{ult}$	0.86	0.78	0.76	-

Fig. 16. Comparison of offset failure stress and ultimate failure stress in QISO-TP and CTT tests

Fig. 17. Comparison of offset failure stress and ultimate failure stress for clamping forces at 5.0 Nm and 0.1 Nm

Fig. 18. Load response and AE amplitude vs. displacement of QISO-TS

Fig. 19. Load response and AE amplitude vs. displacement of QISO-TP

Fig. 20. Load response and AE amplitude vs. displacement of CTT

Fig. 21. Load response and AE amplitude vs. displacement of CMT (the low clamping force)

6. Reference

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Fig. 22 The picture gotten by CT scan. Some damage was above the hole.